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Negotiating design responses in humanitarian crises

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Abstract

Both empathy and design are crucial for the development humanitarian responses to crises. This paper explores the current potential of design to respond to crisis situations to draw the agency of design in humanitarian responses into the academic arena for their presence and collaborative potential to be scrutinized and furthered.

Despite the absence of focused design practices and studies in the humanitarian industry, there have been a number of design actors drawn into the moral imperative of the now highly visible humanitarian responses. With the exploration of these designers a humanitarian-oriented design ethic is emerging: despite not receiving much considered development by the wider design industry. The basis of a ‘humanitarian design’ ethic has started to slowly materialize over the last couple of decades through the practices of a handful of design-focused Not-For-Profit Non-Governmental Organizations. These few established humanitarian design avant-garde have already demonstrated that there is much potential for design work in areas outside of comfortable developed world marketplaces, but how to get there still remains a challenge for many interested parties. In the majority of crisis situations the most pressing questions revolve around locations and their accessibility (physically and virtually), and the accountability of visiting actors to these locations of humanitarian responses.

Exploring the question of where design is aiding humanitarian response to crises, the content of this paper has been drawn from research being undertaken for a doctoral research project on the role of design in humanitarian responses, at the University of Technology, Sydney’s School of Design.

Key words: Humanitarian, Response, Design, Industry, Development

1. An introduction for humanitarian design

For the title of this paper ‘design’ has been abstracted from the International Radiotelephony Spelling Alphabet. How recognizable is this? The question of whether or not many design academics or practitioners would recognize this well established international system of communication (developed in the 1950s by NATO and readily used in military and humanitarian responses), is a query that ties in with the purpose of this paper: designs are inherent to humanitarian crisis responses, yet the research and practice that surround design studies have rarely touched on this important social contribution by the design industry. As an agent in the humanitarian community Design is in its infancy and is only starting to understand interrelatedness and communication in such unconventional marketplaces. Questions of who, what, when, where, and why have barely started to be considered; what exists is the awareness of a need which could be satisfied by design interventions.

Despite the absence of an established design culture within humanitarian responses, design is nonetheless present through artifacts and environments that comprise the humanitarian issues and responses. This noticeable absence is in the situated critique, reflection and practice of design throughout these instances. This critical absence is starting to be addressed along with a growing awareness in the design industry (predominantly via academia) and professional expressions of interest in the responsibilities of design within society [1-7]. However, this comparatively small amount of critique or practice of “designing” for humanitarian development (and/or crisis responses) from recent decades are not only traceable, but have been furthered through design-based or design-related actors [9-23] whose roles lean toward the construction of shelter or enabling scenarios that may involve design skilling, but still largely go unvalued as ‘design’ by the larger International Non-Governmental Organizations (INGOs), or recognized as commercial design. In the few examples of design (whether or not it is called ‘design’), design is the ‘thing’ with which to bridge the humanitarian moral imperative and address the crisis in question. The seminal roles of design in humanitarian responses however, still lack clarity from a social perspective, a design industry perspective, and a humanitarian perspective.

This paper starts to articulate this issue from the design perspective and to outline the current relationship of design and humanitarianism: firstly, through the origins of ‘humanitarian design’ awareness and critique; secondly, through a relation of humanitarianism and design with emotion; and thirdly, by detailing the humanitarian design canon; lastly, tracing the ‘humanitarianism’ embodied by design; and concluding in an overview on furthering the (humanitarian) engagement of design.

Environmental and Systemic design are (of course) vital in the delivery, placement, and use of these artifacts but cannot be uniquely explored within the word-limit of this paper, therefore they will only be discussed in relation to the designed artifacts. Nor are governmental organizations, military, and the delivery of foreign aid (Official Development Assistance) being critiqued in this paper, rather it is the Non-Governmental humanitarian responses where design is currently more visible which are more pressing areas of interest at this point in time, for reasons of accessibility.

This lack of visibility of design as a humanitarian agent is by no means one sided on the part of the designers,

more significant is the lack of recognition by Humanitarian Response Organizations (HROs): design being used in humanitarian responses fades into the inventory and costing lists of crises, and is rarely recognized as 'designed'. This is not a comparative contestation of branding rights between design-team and distributor, but rather an issue of social responsibility for design. A significant negative outcome of this disconnection between designer and distributor is the disabling of potential industrial re-design opportunities, which means that the positive or negative impacts of delivered design is often dependent on the user-actors of the design: a positive outcome of this might be that aid recipients customize an unsuitable design and thereby become 'design agents' themselves, but this is dependent on the user-actor and their opportunity to afford an interpretive use of the design, those without such an opportunity may suffer for their skill short-comings. In crisis situations serious risks are associated with unsuitable designs, and in such circumstances there is no accountability of design impacts.

With the proliferation of socially oriented design organizations since the early 1980s (such as the Buckminster Fuller Institute [1]), there has been a growing curiosity in some socially-minded design circles to strengthen relations with HROs, but many challenges are faced in this competitive field despite the inherent use of 'design' by the humanitarian industries. Primary amongst these issues is the lack of collaborative in-field or logistical access for the purpose of a design response, this may be largely attributable to the need for organizations to demonstrate precedence and therefore credentials for in-field practice, much like most other industry collaborations. Because of the challenges involved in accessing such experiences through HROs, a handful of design-oriented organizations have been established specifically to respond to humanitarian industry issues of shelter directly [13,14,18,21] and with varying levels of response capacity. Accessibility is crucial and highly circumstantial when determining the types of organizational responses possible: humanitarian crises are complex international events, with dynamics that are different to those of the well-established design industries. As there is little precedence for field-based design work in these situations the designer faces greater risk than they otherwise would. In a humanitarian response situation designers (like other humanitarian aid deliverers) need an additional skill-set to work effectively, as well as to physically and psychologically cope with their in-field experiences.

The consciousness of the design industry went global many decades ago, through the works of design critics led initially by Fuller, Papanek, the Margolins, Verbeek [1-7] and volunteer based groups such as the former EcoDesign Foundation [8], who have been questioning the unsustainability of the design industry. Designers have started to become more aware of their potential value to sustainable development, thanks to the contribution of such (predominantly academic) critiques. Concurrently the international humanitarian industry is shifting from state-centric responses to responses mediated by multi-national HRO as well as many smaller Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs). This awakening of socially responsible design thinking (and practice) and the proliferation of potential access points for development assisted by socially responsible design work would seem to be a fortuitous but for the challenges of logistical accessibility (geographic and security), as well as a local lack of physical resource availability combined with the lack of time for reflective practice to avoid repeating the mistakes of past pseudo-colonial humanitarian deliveries: 'humanitarian designers' and design deployers must acknowledge and analyze the developments with which they engage, and assess their potential

impacts to minimize the negative short and long-term ramifications for the locale. This analysis needs to enable individual and state recipient actors into self-determined agents, possibly assisted by expert actors, for the local actors to determine the best course of action for their own future.

The overriding questions of aid-suitability in humanitarian responses and the negative ramifications of ill suited responses are being more frequently voiced from both inside organizations and through the mass media [24-31]. It is this critique rather than increased organizational transparency that are opening avenues to humanitarian access to smaller NGOs. The proliferation of smaller NGOs throughout contemporary humanitarian responses presents some benefits as well as negatives in comparison with the larger governmental responses that are usually coordinated through the key international humanitarian NGO, the United Nations. A key positive point of this evolution of smaller NGOs is the increased number of response organizations increases the potential range of responses and disperses the power of coordinating a humanitarian response, allowing accessibility to more organizations. A key negative point of smaller NGO evolution is that there is also a lessened overall accountability when something does go wrong. There are some safeguards currently being tested to address this issue, such as a leading INGOs delegating responsibility for aspects of a response, such as the facilitation of specific refugee camps by an NGO taking on the role of 'Camp Management Agency' via a Memorandum of Understanding with other NGOs and local parties [32]. In these instances, deliveries can be better coordinated (particularly where there are multiple response sites), and with this there would be greater potential for more effective design implementation (and potential feedback for re-design), if only there were designers to engage in the process.

2. Humanitarianism and emotion

Empathy aids a designer to respond to a concept, client or marketplace; empathy also underpins the altruistic intention aimed through humanitarian responses to transfer across the international stage from individuals / communities / states that enjoy what is arguably a comfortable standard of living, to the individuals / communities / states which struggle to survive from day-to-day as a result of natural or conflict related crises. These expressions of empathy have evolved to try and sate sentiments of moral obligation embodied by the social politics of "developed" societies, but can also mask other motivators such as agendas of state containment for self-preservation. Without defined and agreed contextual parameters, such as a negotiated and enforceable code-of-conduct written into the charter of an organization, empathy is only a beautiful but vulnerable imperative without guarantee and susceptible to less altruistic motivations.

Humanitarian responses are actions founded in humanistic ethical ideologies, traditionally revolving around principles of neutrality between parties to ensure compassion and dignity for all individuals. Echoing the teachings of a few popular religious traditions through predominantly Western social philosophies, as humanitarians we would ideally treat others the way that we would like to be treated. Over the last two decades however this neutrality has been brought into question, as humanitarian INGOs (the United Nations for one) are

starting to be incorporated in government influenced humanitarian responses whilst being tied to a non-violent and impartial ethic, and is thereby limited in capacity to resolve conflict and stabilize a conflict situation. Further challenging the credibility of current international humanitarian procedures are the critics of current international humanitarian practices for their limited ability to deliver beneficial assistance [25,28,29,30]. Humanitarian responses have evolved into a multi-billion dollar industry focusing on highly visible aid deliveries, holding on to the intention of furthering humanistic ideologies of wellbeing through development internationally. This international industry has many organizational flaws that are ingrained in professional practices and therefore difficult to address. With the marketable benefits of in-field media exposure, comes greater exposure to faults and HROs are challenged to balance timely considered responses to crisis situations or else attract criticism by the international mass-media for not responding “soon enough” to a crisis situation.

In terms of design involvement, a key flaw to challenging humanitarian design responses is the resulting dislocation between the humanitarian aid marketplace (deliverer or service provider) and the humanitarian aid recipient. This is reflected in the localized power-play: an INGO inherently acquires a disproportionate allocation of power over a specific environment: if this is coupled with a lack of understanding of the situation but with international pressure to respond rapidly to crisis, situations have the potential to turn crisis locations into a dumping ground for inappropriate aid, and to contribute to an exacerbation of a crisis situation, despite the best of intentions.

Whether aid is appropriate or not is often determined in hindsight of what was delivered, how it was delivered, and how well it responded to the actors (how many and their range of intentions), environmental factors (including natural resource availability), time, accessibility and visibility. The most basic framework through which emergencies are classified by two key types of (non mutually exclusive) humanitarian crises: Humanitarian Emergencies (HEs) which usually result from natural disasters; and, Complex Emergencies (CEs) where human conflict is a significant factor, potentially in addition to a HE. Prior to the 1990s CEs would have been regarded as civil wars and not necessarily responded to in the interventionist manner of contemporary humanitarian activities [33]; predominantly CEs require longer-term assistance, but both HEs and CEs can require long-term or short-term solutions depending on the numerous variables that make each humanitarian disaster unique, but predominantly crisis recovery revolves around issues of autonomy. This uniqueness between disasters has always demanded special consideration in responses, which aid organizations are not necessarily flexible enough to accommodate within a desired response time. Considering this type of practice in ‘design terms’ humanitarian responses can rarely deliver a form that can follow a suited function, but instead deliveries are largely dependent on reactionary responses which, whilst well intentioned have contributed to degrading a situation if the aid delivered was inappropriate for the situation, or easily misappropriated by exploitative local actors such as militia forces: in both cases these are potential issues for the design as well as the delivery of the aid in question.

In recent decades numerous authors have critiqued aspects of the humanitarian response industry, and similarly there are counter critics from within the industry. The subjects broached range from organizational inefficiencies, to site-specific situations, and issues of funding for bureaucracy rather than responding to a humanitarian cause.

The attraction of smaller organizations that seek access to humanitarian crises with their far more modest resources, is a hands-on and more transparent type of response. The modest scale of delivery inherently risking fewer resources and therefore potentially being more conducive as training environments, despite not having the sense of security assumed in larger organizations. The range of professions critiquing inefficiencies in humanitarian responses makes the lack of design analysis all the more obvious. Humanitarian deliverers, economists, psychologists, sociologists, health-care professionals, political analysts, foreign correspondents, regardless of background it would seem that institutional accountability and communication are the favored topics. For these issues to be addressed the humanitarian response industry needs to change their modus operandi, this requires education (or re-education) for practicing transparency and collaborative skills to change the humanitarian community for the better.

In 2004 an article was published in the Humanitarian Exchange Magazine outlining the need for academic involvement in the humanitarian community [34]. As Director of the Feinstein International Famine Center (at Tufts University, UK) and a seasoned humanitarian field-worker, Peter Walker presents four contributions of academia to the humanitarian community: firstly, to develop and maintain a body of skilful and knowledgeable researchers who challenge and enrich an understanding of the humanitarian field; secondly, to develop physical repositories for knowledge (libraries and conferences for example); thirdly, to provide critical and objective advice that private consultancies cannot always provide; lastly, to teach a commonly accepted curriculum, from which a student can graduate with a recognized and relevant qualification. If this were to be applied to design academia, how should the contributions be further defined? This is a conversation that needs to involve both academia and industry of humanitarian issues and design, starting by recognizing where design is present in humanitarian responses. It is this presence that will be elaborated throughout the third part of this paper, ranging through networking and materiality.

3. Outlining the canon of humanitarian design

The presence of design in humanitarian responses is vast albeit largely tacit, as it is frequently embedded in artifacts that are not susceptible to the usual design-marketplace scrutiny: these are circumstances thought to be outside of the usual marketplaces, but this is a misconception, this is another type of marketplace. Besides indigenous designs and designs delivered by HROs, the personal effects brought by humanitarian aid workers also affect the marketplace of a humanitarian response. Humanitarian workers in crisis situations take their everyday consumables with them into environments largely devoid of such a range of consumables, and the presence of these consumables impact on a crisis situation in ways that humanitarian aid deliverers would rarely consider. The false economies that often develop during aid deliveries when the wages and consumer habits of temporary aid workers significantly exceed local capacities for earning money and consuming, far more subversive is “education” of local consumers through newly available produce delivered for the service of international workers. Though this is an interesting topic for further exploration in terms of design, but is a topic that leads away from the focus and word limitation of this paper. Instead the following paper segment will focus

on the presence of design in humanitarian responses, these will be introduced in three parts: virtual networking (websites), designed artifacts, and product oriented development programs.

3.1 - Virtual Networking

Attempting to address the issue of dispersed accountability and poor inter-agency coordination mentioned earlier in the paper, more recent humanitarian programs have seen larger on-site INGOs take-on networking responsibilities coordinating the resources of acting NGOs within a field situation. This allocation of responsibilities is communicated freely through humanitarian response networking websites, developed for professional online coordination and transparency. Generally the design of these websites serves three key purposes: to inform, to network, and to archive. The information available through these websites such as DARA [35], The Sphere Project [36], ReliefWeb [37], and Humanitarian Practice Network [38] are significant and rich with much background information, statistics, and readily accessible contact details. Whilst some have been established since the late 1990s, the majority of networking interfaces have only significantly developed over the last five years, enabled by the greater capacity for social networking programs throughout the Internet. These websites help to coordinate the various stages of many multiple-agency humanitarian responses, such as research and briefing, co-ordination and delivery, distribution and in some cases management, withdrawal and de-briefing. In relation to the deployment of artifacts, some of these websites for humanitarian networks also display a selection of wanted designs for deployment and a point of contact for procurement submissions, these are then compared to determine which design can be best produced for the least expense [39].

By facilitating these online networks inter-agency collaboration can be better coordinated, the duplication of similar humanitarian deliveries can be avoided, as well as increasing the efficiency and transparency of a humanitarian response. The potential greater efficiency and improved coordination is a very positive development for the evolving international aid industry, possibly the most significant offering of these online networks is to network location specific or crisis specific expertise through notice boards [38], and (by sharing these) provide an avenue for individuals to virtually educate themselves in preparation for different locations and types of crises.

3.2 - Artifacts

Artifacts deployed in humanitarian responses range from logistical tools and infrastructure equipment to the basics of humanitarian aid: shelter materials, sanitation systems, and foodstuffs. Whether or not these things are regarded as design themselves, they are dependent on design for their delivery and their use. As previously noted, the consideration of these artifacts as designable tools has otherwise been very limited. Through exhibitions such as *SAFE: Design Takes On Risk*, and *Design for the Other 90%*, their catalogues [40-41], and other recent design publications [42-43] a few humanitarian aid artifacts are given detail. Whilst the *Design Takes on Risk* exhibition displayed design work both as social commentary and design for aid and development, *Design for the Other 90%* provides far more information through the co-published catalogue with a focus on socially-inclusive design:

though the development and deployment of these design works are exemplify locations not threatened by conflict or natural disaster, thereby limiting the application to humanitarian responses.

The list of ‘humanitarian designs’ detailed through these publications includes:

- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees ‘plastic sheeting’ [40];
- United Nations Children’s Fund ‘water container’ [40];
- Doctors Without Borders ‘feeding cup’ [40];
- Doctors Without Borders ‘Bracelet of Life’ middle upper arm circumference measuring device [40];
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees ‘lightweight emergency tent’ [41];
- World Shelters ‘shelter frame kit’ [41];
- Cooperative Housing Foundation International ‘BOLD: Building Opportunities and Livelihoods in Darfur’ [41];
- Ferrara Design Inc. and Architecture for Humanity ‘global village shelters’ [41];
- Brewin and Crawford ‘concrete canvas’ inflatable shelter. Concept only [41];
- United States Army Soldier Systems Center ‘power shade’ [41];
- William Hsu, Art Center College of Design ‘UnBathroom’ disaster latrine. Concept only [41];
- Kristina Drury ‘Sudanese Refugee Cookware’. Concept only [43].

As seen from this list of humanitarian aid-specific designs detailed throughout these publications, after filtering out design as shelter there are few artifacts to exemplify design for humanitarian responses. The artifact designs that are detailed in these publications (with the exception of Hsu and Drury’s contributions as designers) are interesting as examples of a slow co-design process: they have been developed not necessarily by designers, but by field-staff of a particular organization over non-specific periods of time. Though there are relatively few, these designs are nonetheless significant to the humanitarian design canon because of the process through which they have been designed. These artifacts have been developed over the last two decades, and refined in response to functional needs which have been informed by the task-oriented experiences humanitarian field workers, as such they rarely are attributed to a single designer and are instead authored by an organization. These “humanitarian” designs are materially represent the intention for humanistic responses to break from the “charitable” tradition of deploying aid which comprised either appropriated military surplus or discarded second-hand “developed world” donations.

Besides collaborative “non-designer” designs and shelter-oriented practices, the lack of visible design (practice) cultures within larger multi-disciplinary NGOs remains pronounced. Perhaps this absence has gone unchecked by the design industry because of the somewhat abject association of humanitarian responses and the Otherness of such a marketplace, and the ‘design’ associated with desperate utility: a quality that the fashion of design marketing in ‘developed’ societies tends to move away from. This is also reinforced by the tendency of design education to move towards skills dependent on Computer Aided Design rather than traditional hand-crafting skills that tend to be of greater value in crisis situations where there is little if any technology available.

With only a few exceptions such as the predominantly American academic based Rural Studio [11],

Designmatters [15], the Institute Without Boundaries [16], D-Lab [17], Design That Cares [22], Project H Design [23], and the Indian based Honey Bee Network [12]; most design education institutions fail to give students opportunities to explore humanitarian works in their curricula despite an increase of interest in sustainability issues: is sustainable international development less valuable in this area of study? Perhaps this exclusion can still be partially attributed to the sustainable skill lag in favor of the hi-technology push. Whilst built-environment courses in numerous tertiary institutions occasionally offer a special project for students to engage with developing communities, and through such experiences develop field-specific low-technology hands-on skills, further professional practice unfortunately only accessible through predominantly volunteer work with construction or architecture based Not For Profit organizations. For students of design disciplines other than construction and architecture there are few options: even for graphic designers the work remains largely bureaucratic and volunteer based rather than a potential direction for their career. One possible alternative avenue that has gained popularity over the last ten years is the micro-enterprise business model, through which people of a particular locale are enabled to develop and market their indigenous produce and craft to the international marketplace, predominantly through the Internet [44-45]. There is much potential for further design engagements (especially skill-exchanges) in these ventures. But currently these are opportunities better suited to aid for development, rather than aid in response to a humanitarian crisis: but the barriers associated with this are only matters of conceptual and practice-based evolution. The dynamics of the marketplace needs to be rethought.

3.3 - Product-oriented development programs

Micro-enterprises are currently the fashion in humanitarian development programs, favored for their ability to enable people to help themselves, rather than be dependent on the delivery of humanitarian aid. Internationally, the trade of micro-enterprises tends to rely on an artifact-centric cottage industry either utilizing traditional crafts and materials [44], or developing new ones to complement local circumstances [45]. Such co-design-ish ventures have evolved through a combination of grassroots activist movement origins and international facilitation through trade, further supported via the Internet and additional organizational innovations such as micro-financing programs similar to those developed by the Grameen Bank [46]. These innovative businesses loan small amounts of money (which is otherwise difficult to earn in these locales) negotiated for more feasible in-kind repayment by borrower/s.

That these programs provide for and sustain local livelihoods, as well as preserve local skills and crafts makes them extraordinarily valuable as bastions of cultural diversity. Though traditionally marketed and undertaken in stabilized humanitarian development programs, there are examples of these types of ventures undertaken by individuals and part of programs within refugee camp situations as well. As the technologies used are flexible, portable, and materials are often sourced locally, these design ventures provide an excellent opportunity for individuals to regain self-determination in otherwise adverse circumstances. But like the camps where these ventures find a foothold there is a typical and undeniable transience to their business: the local marketplace is short-term, the resources for developing the venture are usually finite and dictated by the locale.

Reflecting on what currently comprises the published humanitarian design canon, it must be noted that there are designs that have become part of the long-standing General Issue stock of humanitarian responses, which make up the goods usually delivered by HROs. Related designs sourced via the military designs have also not been acknowledged here. Of the design works which have been collected, categorized and published, the 'humanitarian design' canon comprises: approximately 23 designer instigated humanitarian projects since 1972 (though only two of these were before 1993); 10 publications: predominantly brief canon catalogues, rather than critiques of humanitarian designs, since 2001; 1997 saw the first of approximately 4 student or young-designer oriented humanitarian design competitions [47-50]; since 1983 there have been at least 6 highly visible expressions of humanitarian activism in design practices, such as artworks such as the work of Studio Orta [51-52]; and at least 6 documented non-designer humanitarian designs since 1985, previously discussed as in-field developed artifacts. This abstract humanitarian design canon only just touches 50 arguable caches of 'humanitarian design' practice, and the majority of them have only presented over the last decade. Though the acknowledged presence of design practice may be thin, between consumer and design practices is a different matter, and where some of the most effective (albeit currently challenging to define) examples of design can be found. The problem with these "designs" is that their benefit cannot be generalized: their effect is largely dependent on personal emotional engagements, and subsequently circumstantial in their ability to aid recipients beyond a "delivery" of humanitarianism: here the fate of a design is largely beyond the product designer in favor of a design-skill educator.

4. Design and emotion in humanitarian responses

Whilst aiming for physical improvements in crisis situations it is important to note the value of humanitarian responses beyond a physical security [53] and the role of design in providing this: the blanket; the photograph; the dress; the water container; the tarpaulin: artifacts that have been made by design and delivered by design are consumables that mark the temporal experiences of displaced persons, which often have no other marker within the precarious time-frame of displacement experiences. Whether delivered via aid or made locally, everyday consumables frequently become portable mementos of pre-displacement living for remembrance during displacement from ones home/habitat. From comparatively traumatic personal accounts of artifacts taking on the role of empathy prosthetic such as Ruth First's relishing the recording of days in stitches on the back of her dressing-gown lapel throughout one of her incarcerations [54], or Elaine Scarry's example of Sheila Cassidy's hope in the "civility" of a white linen handkerchief during her Chilean incarceration [55]; to more literal communications through artifacts such as Afghani war rugs, and Hmong Pa'ndau story-cloths. Artifacts can carry an intended or circumstantial sense of place or connectivity whether on an individual or cultural level, they can be consumed for the purpose of nourishment, to demonstrate power, to communicate, and can generate evidence of habits and interactions to the extent of supporting an otherwise intangible aspect of cultural heritages. Such artifacts make the heritage of displacement tangible and acknowledgeable not only by the individual and group, but to the rest of society who come into contact with the artifacts through open events like commemorative services or exhibitions. The New South Wales Migrant Heritage Centre's *Belongings* virtual exhibition [56] is one such collection detailing mementoes of displacement. In such instances design acts as a

mediators of journeys that cannot yet be fully articulated through more easily interpreted forms of communication.

It is usually of little relevance to the user whether or not their consumables are called 'design': it is the range of utility and/or the role of the object as memento that is important. Here designs are frequently in the process of being re-crafted by the user, and mass-produced items are customized over time by users to suit their needs and out of necessity, as previously mentioned the actor becomes agent. The exciting aspect of such situations is the practice and evolution of skills that potentially enable people to determine how they will work out of a state of crisis, possible aid dependency, or potential victim mentality and other psychological trauma resulting from a displacement experience; in addition to this value is the potential for the crafted artifacts to embody the otherwise intangible heritage of refugee experiences whether the artifact is tangible, photographed, or otherwise rendered.

5. Furthering (humanitarian) involvement

This paper has identified the current presence of 'humanitarian' design (by intention or by inherence) through its slow evolution since the 1980s, and discussed avenues for increasing the presence of 'humanitarian design' for improved collaboration and accountability between the design and humanitarian industries to better honor the empathetic intentions of humanitarianism. To summarize, the basis of this collaboration needs to be built with the education of designers abilities to create and utilize low-technology skills, so that design skill are suited to their fields of employment and not just centered on the application of Computer Aided Design. There is potential for low-technology collaborations to develop and further the design presence within the humanitarian community by extending the practice of education-based programs, the valuing of displacement heritages, as well as strengthening the capacity of construction based Not-For-Profit organizations already established.

Similar to the critical and educational academic contributions to sustainable design and humanitarian studies cited earlier in the paper, an increase of critical design contributions to humanitarian responses could be utilized to develop skills and knowledge for industry as well as localized self-determination, both remotely as well as in-field. The practice of design itself: underpinned by the necessary undertaking of research to justify, develop, produce, and review a work, could help to provide critical and objective study of crisis situations and empathetic responses to them through the various arenas of humanitarian practice: in the field, industry, or educational institution. A strong collaboration between design and humanitarian practices would benefit both industries: designers would gain an avenue to explore more challenging areas of practice outside of current commercial marketplaces, and even to exchange skills for sustainable practice with the slower technologies of less developed consumer cultures; and, giving the humanitarian industry greater capacity to respond to (and thereby empathize with) the uniqueness of each situation, to focus on enabling self-development rather than delivering indifferent generic products as humanitarian responses.

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